

Evaluating the Impact of Training and Applying Modern Making Skills on Students' Self-Assessed Confidence and Improvement

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Abstract

Instructors that utilize makerspace resources for hands-on education are interested in the effectiveness of their curriculum. Rather than referencing instructors' evaluation, this study focuses on metrics of confidence and improvement from the students' perspective. The students' self-assessment of their ability to use modern making skills was collected before and after completing the freshmen course Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering at Carnegie Mellon University. It was found that the students' self-efficacy improved from the training and applications throughout the course.

Introduction

The proliferation of makerspaces in schools and communities has been concurrent with the Maker Movement, which employs a theory of learning with a "focus on problem solving and digital and physical fabrication" [1]. In higher educational institutions, digital and physical fabrication resources are often used for prototyping, especially by senior capstone courses [2]. These programs have students develop prototypes to act as a proof-of-concept of their technical designs. This allows real-world applications of students' engineering knowledge in an educational environment.

For leaders of these makerspaces, training new users to access software, tools, and equipment is the foundation for safe operation of these facilities. A wide variety of methods for training are utilized, ranging from online to in-person to blended formats [3]–[5]. Regardless of the method, it is assumed that instructors are invested in the effectiveness of their training. Most often, students' knowledge is evaluated by the instructor, either as pass/fail or numerically scoring assignments based on the quality of completed work. These scores are commonly accepted as an indicator of students' understanding of concepts, for which higher scores are accepted as students having learned more [6]–[8].

In contrast to depending on instructor scores, some researchers have proposed focusing on self-efficacy as a better metric of students' motivations and outcomes

[9]–[11]. The concept of self-efficacy was originally proposed by Bandura, who defined it as "an individuals' judgment of their capability to organize and execute courses of action for a given task" [12]. A complementary definition of self-efficacy from Speier and Frese is given as "the notion that one can bring about positive results through one's own actions" [13]. In academic makerspaces, trained students must step up to the task of planning, fabricating, and prototyping to produce tangible results. Therefore, it is expected that subsequent to training, a useful measure of success is the degree of confidence that students have in their ability to utilize software, tools, and equipment.

This paper conducts a study on the self-efficacy of students enrolled in a freshman level engineering course at Carnegie Mellon University. This course, Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering, includes teaching students modern making skills of CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting, and physical computing. This course is a prerequisite for the core curriculum of the Mechanical Engineering (MechE) undergraduate program, in part because students are required to use these skills to build functional prototypes of their sophomore, junior, and senior engineering design projects.

This study aims to answer these questions using data from a pre-course and post-course survey of students:

1. Was students' confidence in their ability to apply each modern making skill higher at the end of the course than beginning of the course?
2. For each modern making skill, was the change in students' confidence between the beginning and end of the course correlated to their personally identified improvement during the course?
3. For students that do not identify as having the highest level of confidence in their abilities, at what point in the process of using the software, tool, or equipment does doubt originate from?

Methods

This study uses data collected from surveying students in the Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering course during the spring semester of 2023. On the first day of class, prior to beginning instruction, students were presented with a pre-course survey electronically. Training students in modern making skills was distributed throughout the course. This training was a blend of both online instruction via Pre-Lab and in-person instruction at Laboratory. Students applied this training in CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting, and physical computing towards 2 of 3 individual challenges outlined in Figure 1 and Figure 2, as well as 1 group project outlined in Figure 3. The 3rd of 3 challenges was on the topic of thermal-fluids-energy, but did not specifically necessitate use of the students' modern making skills. During the last week of the semester, students were presented with a post-course survey electronically.

Figure 1: Challenge – Solid Mechanics
Topic: hand-powered LED flashlight
Skills: CAD modeling the assembly, 3D printing the motor holder, laser cutting the gearbox

Figure 2: Challenge – Control Systems
Topic: play the red light green light game
Skills: physical computing with robot car kits

Figure 3: Project – MechE
Topic: avoid putting humans in hazardous situations, send a robot car into a steam tunnel
Skills: CAD modeling the valve manipulator, 3D printing or laser cutting the valve manipulator, physical computing with robot car kits to traverse the steam tunnel to reach the valve

List of brands used during training:

- CAD modeling: SolidWorks Educational Edition
- 3D printing: Creality Ender 3
- Laser cutting: Epilog Helix / Fusion Pro 48
- Physical computing: Arduino Uno, Elegoo car kit

At Carnegie Mellon University, all of the engineering departments offer one freshman level introductory course each semester. The Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering serves as that course for the Department of Mechanical Engineering. Since every engineering undergraduate student is required to complete two introductory courses, non-MechE students also complete this course each academic year. In the spring semester of 2023, a total of 61 students completed the Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering course. These students had a response rate of 80% (n=49) for completing both the pre-course and post-course survey. Any response to one survey but not the other was not used in this study.

The pre-course and post-course surveys shared two questions about each of the four maker skills: CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting, and physical computing. For all four sets of questions, the first was a more simple task and the second was a more complex task to achieve. The variation in intricacy was twofold, the first question stated something would be given that was useful to achieving the task and the second question had a higher quantity of components needed to achieve the task. For all eight of these questions, the multiple-choice answers were identical. From a 5-point Likert-style scale, students selected either “not at all confident,” “not so confident,” “somewhat confident,” “very confident,” or “extremely confident” in their ability to conduct the task.

In the post-course survey only, there were four additional questions included for each modern making skill. The first question (more simple task) in each set was followed by three new questions. These were used to break down that task into its major steps and had the same multiple-choice answers as listed previously. The second question (more complex task) was followed by one new question that asked to what degree did the students’ ability to use that modern making skill improve during the course. From a 5-point Likert-style scale, students selected either “not at all improved,” “slightly improved,” “moderately improved,” “greatly improved,” or “extremely improved.”

The multiple-choice confidence responses were mapped to numeric values:

- 1 – “not at all confident”
- 2 – “not so confident”
- 3 – “somewhat confident”
- 4 – “very confident”
- 5 – “extremely confident”

By mapping the students’ responses to numeric values, it is possible to quantify the trends, such as changes in responses. The amount of change in confidence on questions between the pre-course and post-course surveys was calculated as number from post-course minus number from pre-course survey. This method results in 4 being the maximum amount a student can increase their confidence (5 from “extremely confident” minus 1 from “not at all confident”).

The multiple-choice improvement responses were mapped to numeric values:

- 1 – “not at all improved”
- 2 – “slightly improved”
- 3 – “moderately improved”
- 4 – “greatly improved”
- 5 – “extremely improved”

It is of interest to check for a correlation between change in confidence and amount of improvement by the end of the course. This method results in 1 being the minimum amount (0 from no change in confidence plus 1 from “not at all improved”) and 9 being the maximum amount (4 from most change in confidence plus 5 from “extremely improved”).

Results & Discussion

It was expected that students’ confidence in their ability to conduct modern making skills would be lower in the pre-course survey, because this was prior to initiating instruction. After receiving instruction in modern making skills through Pre-Labs (outside class) and Laboratories (in-class), students applied their skills to multiple individual challenges and a group project with topics in mechanical engineering. Due to experience from hands-on training and applications, it was predicted that students’ confidence would be higher in the post-course survey. By comparing the aggregate responses in the pre-course survey to the post-course survey, this expected trend was observed from levels of confidence being lower in Figure 4 and higher in Figure 5 for the more simple task. This trend was also found for the more complex task, observed from levels of confidence being lower in Figure 6 and higher in Figure 7.

Figure 4: The frequency of responses regarding students' confidence in their ability to conduct the more simple task, the first of two questions in the pre-course survey.

Figure 5: The frequency of responses regarding students' confidence in their ability to conduct the more simple task, the first of two questions in the post-course survey.

Figure 6: The frequency of responses regarding students' confidence in their ability to conduct the more complex task, the second of two questions in the pre-course survey.

Figure 7: The frequency of responses regarding students' confidence in their ability to conduct the more complex task, the second of two questions in the post-course survey.

The change in confidence between the pre-course and post-course survey was examined for each student individually. From the numerical mapping of responses, and conducting a subtraction of post-course value minus pre-course value, the data in Figure 8 is used to show that on average students' confidence level increased by 2.0 steps for the simple tasks. A similar trend was also found for the complex tasks, as the data in Figure 9 is used to identify that on average students' confidence level increased by 1.6 steps.

Figure 8: The frequency of change in confidence on the more simple task, the first of two questions on both pre-course and post-course surveys.

Figure 9: The frequency of change in confidence on the more complex task, the second of two questions on both pre-course and post-course surveys.

For each modern making skill, students identified their improvement on the post-course survey. It was expected that experience from hands-on training and applications would result in students identifying improvement to their modern making skills at the end of the course. The aggregate responses in Figure 10 is used to show that the majority of students determined that they had a significant amount of improvement by the end of the course.

Figure 10: The frequency of students' improvement during the course, collected only on the post-course survey.

It was predicted that if students accurately indicated high confidence on the pre-course survey, they would not learn a significant amount of modern making skills and rate their improvement as low on the post-course survey. In contrast, it was predicted that if students accurately indicated low confidence on the pre-course survey, they would learn a significant amount of modern making skills and rate their improvement as high on the post-course survey. The method used to check for a correlation between change in confidence and amount of improvement by the end of the course was the addition of these two numbers. The results for each students' change in confidence value plus improvement value is shown in Figure 11 for the more simple task and Figure 12 for the more complex task. In general, these Gaussian-like distributions align with the expectation that students starting the course without significant knowledge of modern making skills gained more confidence and recognized the positive improvement in their abilities. Conversely students that already possessed modern making skills prior to taking the course retained their confidence without notable improvement in their abilities. This analysis of data can be used to assert that the laboratory curriculum in the course set a baseline for modern making skills among the majority of students. In outcome, there was an achievement in the course goal of preparing the majority of students to employ modern making skills for hands-on projects in subsequent core MechE curriculum.

Figure 11: The frequency of students' improvement during the course plus the change in confidence on the more simple task.

Figure 12: The frequency of students' improvement during the course plus the change in confidence on the more complex task.

In only the post-course survey, subsequent to the more simple task question were three questions that identified the major steps in the process of completing that task. The expectation was that these questions could be used to identify the breakdown in confidence. The response by students for each of the three questions could have a confidence level lower, the same, or higher than the answer to the first question. For each student, a count was made of how many times none, some, or all of the three steps had a response with a confidence level different than the simple task. The result for each student was used to determine that the majority of students did not indicate a difference in confidence on steps being lower in Figure 13 nor higher in Figure 14 compared to the entire task (value of 0 from 1-1, 2-2, 3-3, 4-4, or 5-5). These outcomes do not support that there was a particular step in the process that is suppressing students' confidence in completing the simple task.

Figure 13: The frequency of students indicating lower confidence on none, some, or all (0-3) of the three steps to complete the simple task than the entire task itself.

Figure 14: The frequency of students indicating higher confidence on none, some, or all (0-3) of the three steps to complete the simple task than the entire task itself.

Conclusion

The analysis conducted in this study was used to confirm that students' self-assessed confidence and improvement was impacted by the training and application of modern making skills throughout the course.

- The students' perceived confidence in their ability to use modern making skills increased, both for a simple task and a complex task.
- The students perceived improvement in their ability to use modern making skills increased.
- Students in this course shared a similar level of combined confidence and improvement, which sets a baseline of knowledge for further use of modern making skills in subsequent curriculum.

These outcomes would be useful in identifying students that had low self-efficacy in their modern making skills. It would be an option to target these students with invitations to conduct topic reviews or join supplementary activities in the makerspace. In such a situation, the self-efficacy of such students could continue to be tracked for changes in confidence and improvement to their modern making skills.

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